

FEATURES OF THE FORMATION OF OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH MOTIVATION OF FUTURE PHYSIOTHERAPISTS

Vyshar Ye.V.

*senior lecturer of social work and special education
Poltava Institute of Economics and Law
Monastyrska street, 6, Poltava, Ukraine*

Abstract

The article reveals the relevance and peculiarities of the formation of professional health motivation of future physical therapists. It was determined that one of the main means of developing future specialists and forming occupational health motivation in them is the content of education, which is determined by the purpose and tasks of education at a certain stage of the development of society and is the basis of the formation of professional competence - the basis of occupational health motivation. The effective formation of students' professional health motivation will take place through compliance with the organizational-pedagogical, moral-ecological, psychological-pedagogical, search-research conditions of study of academic disciplines.

Keywords: educational process, students, motivation, professional health, physical therapists, content of education, pedagogical conditions, game, spirituality, morality.

The main source of a motive for an individual's activity is a need, it is precisely this that generates interest. Therefore, for the practical implementation of today's educational requirements, when building the educational process of higher education institutions, one should take care of the personal significance of professional health for each student, understanding it as a necessary and attractive personal need, while not weakening the latter's orientation to meeting public needs, that is, socially useful activity. Considering this, the traditional educational tasks of forming basic professional competences (knowledge, abilities and skills for the safe performance of professional duties) are insufficient for the effective formation of occupational health motivation, they must be combined with elements of comprehensive professional socialization of students, i.e. the formation of a worldview in accordance with social values, motivations of behavior. In particular, H. Hryban notes that, in addition to knowledge and skills, the main criteria for the readiness of future specialists for health-related activities are motivation [1, p. 37].

Motivation is a synthesis of the individual's intellectual knowledge and external stimuli that determine the means of action, encourage socially useful activities and focus on the achievement of personal and social goals; this is a self-conscious attraction to meeting needs, success in life and providing benefit to society. The occupational health motivation system should ideally ensure both the satisfaction of the needs of the physical therapist himself and the successful satisfaction of the social needs of the latter, i.e. social health.

One of the main means of development of future physical therapists and the formation of professional health motivation in them is the content of education, which is determined by the purpose and tasks of education at a certain stage of the development of society and is the basis of the formation of professional competence - the basis of professional health motivation. The content of education in our understanding is a system of scientific competencies,

the mastery of which will ensure the comprehensive development of mental and physical abilities of students, the formation of their worldview, morals and behavior, preparation for a safe social life, in particular, and industrial activity. It includes four components: experience of cognitive activity (knowledge), experience of performing known methods of activity (ability to act according to a model), experience of creative activity (making non-standard decisions in atypical situations) and positive motivation of professional health (optimal combination of individual and social needs). The listed components of the content of education are closely interrelated: without knowledge, there is no skill, knowledge and skills are the basis of creative activity, and the activity expresses the ideals and convictions of the individual, that is, his worldview, motivation of behavior. A person becomes a professional, a master of his craft as he masters the system of knowledge, learns certain norms of behavior. The richer the individual's world of knowledge, the more effective and targeted the selection and growth of new knowledge, their transition into motives for behavior and activity.

We have determined that the effective formation of the professional health motivation of future physical therapists will take place through the observance of organizational-pedagogical, moral-ecological, psychological-pedagogical, research-research conditions of study of educational disciplines. Organizational and pedagogical conditions provide for a comprehensive approach to the study of the discipline using interdisciplinary connections; rational choice and combination of traditional forms and methods of learning with practical activities and game modeling. The choice of the game as the dominant form of organization of classes is determined by the specifics of occupational hazards, the overcoming and prevention of which is of a collective nature. In addition, collective educational activity has significant potential opportunities for the formation of optimal educational motivation of students (self-affirmation, duty, self-improvement, professional, cognitive, communicative

and empathetic motives) [4, p. 144]. The game ensures the realization of the following educational goals: didactic: expanding one's horizons, cognitive activity, application and formation of knowledge, skills, and abilities; educational: education of independence, will, cooperation, collectivism, communicativeness, sociability; developmental: development of attention, memory, thinking, imagination, creative abilities, ability to compare and contrast, motivation of educational activities; socializing: involvement in society's norms and values, adaptation to environmental conditions, socialization [5, p. 8-9].

Moral and ecological conditions will provide a valuable approach to the environment; continuity of greening. After all, the promotion of a moral attitude towards the environment should become a mandatory component of the formation of the professional health motivation of a physical therapist. The means of promoting moral behavior are the disclosure in the content of the discipline of the beautiful in a person. When training future specialists, it is necessary to form not only traditional theoretical competence, but also to introduce a "human" understanding of the consequences of activity, built on a humanistic basis. After all, the meaning of life activity is not reduced to the accumulation of material values that disappear in the process of use, but is revealed in bringing benefit to society, harmony with oneself and the environment.

Psychological and pedagogical conditions are a systematic, continuous motivation for the formation of professional health. This pedagogical condition is implemented in practice using two ways: giving negative examples of the lack of professional health (adverse impact on nature and society) and positive examples of self-realization and recognition in society under the condition of professional health (examples from the professional activities of successful and recognized in the society of physical therapists, etc.).

Search and research conditions ensure the development of students' creative abilities, taking into account their personal abilities and interests; creation of space for the development of non-standard thinking (writing abstracts and scientific articles, participation in scientific conferences and research works, creating projects, etc.).

To model a worldview, the content side of which is an orientation to the motivation of occupational health, taking into account the observance of the above-mentioned pedagogical conditions, we propose to integrate elements of the content of occupational health into the content of the disciplines. The content of the concept of occupational health in our understanding should include the experience of safe professional activity, which is embodied together with knowledge in the abilities and skills of the individual; experience of creative, searching activities to solve new problems that society faces; experience of a valuable attitude to the environment. We built the selection of the specified system of principles on the basis of the experience of leading scientists in the relevant scientific field.

The age-old experience of effective implementation of education and upbringing, clarified by scientific research, was embodied in the first

attempts to create a complete system of education principles by Ya. Comenskyi, J. Pestalozzi, F. Disterweg, and K. Ushinskyi. In modern scientific research on the selection of teaching principles, the works of M. Skatkin, I. Lerner, Yu. Babanskyi, V. Bezpalko, and V. Krajevskyi, who developed a number of didactic concepts of the content of education and teaching methods that embody knowledge, skills and abilities, are devoted. Among the variety of scientific works dedicated to the formation of the content of education, the vision of V. Kraevsky and I. Lerner, which is applicable to the formation of the professional health motivation of future physical therapists, who see inclusion in the structure of the content as a condition for the formation of a comprehensively developed spiritual personality, ready for self-actualization and life creativity education of the four elements of social experience: knowledge about nature, society, thinking, technology and methods of activity already acquired by society; the experience of implementing known methods of activity, which is embodied in the skills and abilities of the person who carries out this experience; experience of creative, searching activities in solving new problems that arise before society; the experience of attitude to the world, to each other, that is, a system of emotional, volitional, ecological, moral, aesthetic education [3].

Taking into account the scientific achievements of outstanding teachers of the past and present and our own pedagogical experience, we identified the main principles of selecting and structuring the content of training, which will ensure the quality formation of the motivation of professional health - the principle of the formation of theoretical studies of disciplines on a humanistic basis and the principle of the connection of science with professional activity. The above principles are consistent with the features of the formation of professional competence, which occurs in the following sequence: 1) obtaining theoretical knowledge that helps to understand the essence, assess the harmfulness or danger to life of a certain dangerous factor; 2) an assessment of optimal ways to overcome health hazards, consistent with one's own knowledge and capabilities; 3) overcoming dangers or preventing them, guided by one's own value system. In our opinion, the determining factor in assessing the formation of the motivation of professional health should be the identification of spirituality. Spirituality is manifested through the individual expression in the system of personal motives of two fundamental needs: knowledge and social realization; it is characterized by a positive attitude towards the environment, care, attention to people, readiness to always come to the rescue. The objective benefit of spiritual professional activity is dialectically connected with their subjective selflessness, where the highest satisfaction is knowledge and transformation of the surrounding world for the benefit of the environment.

Therefore, the pedagogical conditions for the effective formation of professional health motivation are a complex of organizational-pedagogical, moral-ecological, psychological-pedagogical and search-research tools. The implementation of the specified

pedagogical conditions will allow to develop worldview beliefs of future agrarians, which involve awareness of the following aspects: the need for the formation of professional health; the importance of a valuable attitude to the surrounding world; the importance of a healthy lifestyle; own responsibility for preserving people's health; the social value of spiritual health along with physical and mental health; the importance of professional competence in the field of health care for successful self-realization in society.

Our study does not exhaust the problem of formation of motivation for professional health. The theoretical and methodical principles of the formation of the motivation of the professional health of future specialists in the process of studying the disciplines of the professional direction and in the future professional activity require further scientific research.

References

1. Hryban H. P. Modernization of the modern methodological system of physical education of students of agrarian universities / H. Hryban // *Pedagogy, psychology and medical and biological problems of*

physical education and sports. 2012. No. 9. - P. 37. [Published in Ukrainian]

2. Goncharenko S. U. Pedagogical research: methodological advice to young scientists / Goncharenko Semyon Ustimovych. – K.; Vinnytsia: DoV "Vinnytsia", 2008. - 278 p. [Published in Ukrainian]

3. Kraevsky V. Theoretical principles of the content of general secondary education [sub. ed. V. V. Kraevsky, I. Ya. Lerner]. - M.: *Pedagogyka*, 1983. - p. 146. [Published in Ukrainian]

4. L. Voloshko. The formation of educational motivation as a condition for academic success of students / Larisa Voloshko // *Organizational and methodological support of students' independent work: state, problems, prospects: materials XXXXI scientific-method. conf. / Poltava state Agrarian Academy.* - Poltava, 2010. - P. 142–144. [Published in Ukrainian]

5. Khlebnikova T. M. Business game as a method of active teacher training: education. method. manual for lecturers, students / T. M. Khlebnikova. - Kh.: *Osnova*, 2005. - 80 p.